

Automated Design of Add-Ons for Soft Hands

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Abstract—Soft robotic hands allow the exploitation of hand-object-environment interactions, but their capabilities can still be limited in cluttered or narrow spaces. In this abstract, we propose enhancing the versatility of soft grippers by adding passive components to their structure without completely altering their design and control. These add-ons are prototyped through a data-driven automated design procedure and their effectiveness has been proved with experiments using two different hands.

Index Terms—Grasping, Grippers, Soft Robot Design

I. INTRODUCTION

Designing robotic grasping systems capable of handling several different objects in unstructured and possibly cluttered environments still remains an open challenge. To tackle this problem, the *soft manipulation* approach has proposed to adopt soft robotic grippers able to safely comply with the surroundings, allowing the implementation of novel grasping strategies which deliberately exploit the hand-object-environment interactions. Moreover, the hand design can be enriched by adding soft-rigid structures which facilitate these interactions as done in [1], where the authors present to attach scoop-like rigid structures to the hand palm.

Recently, we introduced a new strategy, i.e., *scoop grasp*, to simplify the grasp execution when objects are constrained from one or two sides [2]. This strategy can be exploited by hands embedding suitably designed constraints in their structure.

In this abstract, we propose an automated procedure for designing soft-rigid scoop-shaped passive inclusions that can be added to commercial or custom grippers to enable new grasping strategies (see Fig. 1) and enlarge the set of graspable objects [3]. Thus, we introduce a method where interchangeable scoops allow to perform scoop grasps with any gripper.

Our method was validated with two different soft hands, the Soft ScoopGripper [1] and the Pisa/IIT SoftHand [4]. We demonstrated that even robotic hands which do not have embedded constraints in their initial design can benefit from these additions, enlarging the set of graspable objects and of possible grasping strategies.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The first step of our method consisted in finding the optimal parameters to design the scoops and position them into the structure of the chosen hands. We modelled the kinematics of the two adopted hands and implemented the simulation of quasi-static grasps of 50 different objects. A top-grasp

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Fig. 1: Adding a scoop-shaped add-on to a soft hand: pre-grasp configuration, and final grasp.

was iteratively generated by closing the simulated hand over the object model until the optimal combination of decision variables was selected by the solver. We decided to include a model of the environment into the design optimization. In particular, we added a wall-like environmental constraint to each object model. The vector \mathbf{x} of decision variables of the optimization problem contains the positioning and the size of the scoop.

The optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\max_{\mathbf{x}} GQI(\mathbf{x}) + \frac{1}{1 + \Delta_{\gamma}(\mathbf{x})}. \quad (1)$$

The two components of the cost function are a grasp quality index (GQI) and a term which considers the scoop, object and constraint orientations. The obtained scoops are thus optimized to perform scoop grasps from the top exploiting wall-like constraints and their design features are fed into the second step of the automated design procedure.

As it would be unfeasible to prototype as many different scoops, we decided to reduce the number of scoops using a clustering algorithm.

We modelled each candidate scoop using a Gaussian Mixture Model Ω to get a probabilistic encoding of the joint distribution $P(\hat{\mathbf{x}}|\Omega)$. We obtained 3 and 4 scoops for the SSG and the Pisa/IIT SoftHand, respectively.

To 3D-print the scoops and the flexible hinges to attach them to the hand palm, we used ABS-M30. The mechanism to attach the scoops to the hands has to be designed according to the optimization results and the adopted hand.

Then, to make it possible to use the prototyped scoops in grasping tasks, we developed a 3D Convolutional Neural Network capable of selecting the most suitable scoop for grasping a certain object with a certain hand. The training dataset was composed by a voxel grid converted from a partial point cloud, labelled by the grasp success rate of each scoop.

TABLE I: Objects size, output of the CNN and grasp success rates obtained from Experiment 1.

ID	Object	Size [mm]	Mass [g]	Output CNN			Success Rate		
				Scoop 1A	Scoop 1B	Scoop 1C	Scoop 1A	Scoop 1B	Scoop 1C
1	tennis ball	$\varnothing 65$	59.4	0.56	0.14	0.16	6/10	2/10	2/10
2	body spray	$\varnothing 45 \times 175$	34	0.34	0.67	0.17	4/10	6/10	0/10
3	white box	$90 \times 175 \times 60$	146	0.29	0.32	0.47	2/10	4/10	6/10

Fig. 2: Success rates for (a) Exp. 2 and (b) Exp. 3.

The voxel grid included voxels belonging to the constraint itself to discern the same object in different poses with respect to the constraint.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We executed three batches of experimental trials to demonstrate different hypotheses. First, we tested each scoop of the SSG on three objects with prototypical shapes to prove that the scoop having the highest success probability according to the CNN actually performs better than the others on previously unseen objects (Table I). The second experiment (Fig. 2a) aimed at testing the optimal scoops of the SSG suggested by the CNN (Fig. 3a) and at comparing their effectiveness with respect to the scoop originally designed in [1]. In the third experiment, we tested the scoops designed for the Pisa/IIT SoftHand (Fig. 3b). We compared obtained results by repeating the same experimental trials removing the designed add-ons. The aim was to study if embedded constraints can represent an aid in case of restrained scenarios, where the hand cannot proficiently use the environment (Fig. 2b).

In all the experimental trials involving the use of a scoop, we carried out the following steps. The object to be grasped was placed close to a vertical surface. The vision algorithm recognizes the 3D point cloud of the object-constraint pair, which is converted into a 3D voxel grid and fed to the CNN. Lastly, the outcome of the network provided us with the optimal scoop to be mounted on the hand. Hence, the robot was moved towards the vertical surface placing the scoop plate parallel to it. A grasp was considered successful if the object was picked up and moved to the final position without falling. Otherwise, it was deemed to be unsuccessful.

Fig. 3: Examples of grasps from Experiments 2 and 3.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results shown in the Table I provide us with two main insights: *i*) the scoop suggested by the network coincides with the one providing the highest success rate in the experiments, and *ii*) overall, the values of the CNN predicted success rates are comparable with the experimentally obtained ones.

In Experiment 2, the overall success rate of the trials carried out with the optimal scoop is 80% against 45% of those performed considering the original scoop. This means that the newly designed scoops outperform the original ones.

Experiment 3 aimed at demonstrating that the presented methodology can be applied to hands designed without foreseeing any additional parts to enhance their performance. Overall, the experimental trials performed with the hand equipped with the optimal scoop present higher success rates (79%) than without it (40%).

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In conclusion, we proposed an automated design procedure that is general enough to be applied to components with different shapes which can be added to robotic grippers to increase their versatility (e.g., scoop-like structures, nails).

Future works will focus on automating the insertion of the add-ons in the gripper structure. The inclusion of simple but effective parts in commercial hands allows to adapt the same device to different tasks, e.g., in fast-changing production lines where substituting the end-effector is time-consuming.

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